

Contribution to the knowledge of the fauna of the family Pyramidellidae Gray, 1840 (Mollusca, Gastropoda) on the islands of Saint Helena and Ascension

Contribución al conocimiento de la fauna de la familia Pyramidellidae Gray, 1840 (Mollusca, Gastropoda) de las Islas de Santa Elena y Ascensión

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ABSTRACT

The Pyramidellidae of the islands of Saint Helena and Ascension are studied. New information is provided on the Pyramidellids described in the work of SMITH (1890a). Five species new to science are described: *Cingulina boirai* n. sp., *Miralda verhaeghei* n. sp., *Parthenina stanyi* n. sp., *Odostomia lucsegersi* n. sp. and *Odostomia templadoi* n. sp. Syntypes of *Obeliscus* (*Syrnola*) *sanctae-helenae*, *Obeliscus* (*Syrnola*) *pumilio*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides*, *Turbonilla haroldi*, *Turbonilla brachia*, *Turbonilla assimilans*, *Leucotina minuta* and *Odostomia glaphyra* are figured. A lectotype is designated for *Turbonilla* (*Dunkeria*) *eritima*, considered a synonym of *T. assimilans*. New generic allocations are proposed for seven species.

RESUMEN

Se estudian los Pyramidellidae de las islas de Santa Elena y Ascensión. Se aporta nueva información sobre los Pyramidellidos descritos en el trabajo de SMITH (1890a). Se describen cinco especies nuevas para la ciencia: *Cingulina boirai* n. sp., *Miralda verhaeghei* n. sp., *Parthenina stanyi* n. sp., *Odostomia lucsegersi* n. sp. y *Odostomia templadoi* n. sp. Se han figurado sintipos de *Obeliscus* (*Syrnola*) *sanctae-helenae*, *Obeliscus* (*Syrnola*) *pumilio*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides*, *Turbonilla haroldi*, *Turbonilla brachia*, *Turbonilla assimilans*, *Leucotina minuta* y *Odostomia glaphyra*. Se designa un lectotipo de *Turbonilla* (*Dunkeria*) *eritima*, considerada sinónimo de *T. assimilans*. Se proponen nuevas asignaciones genéricas para siete especies.

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KEY WORDS: Pyramidellidae, Saint Helena, Ascension.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Pyramidellidae, Santa Elena, Ascensión.

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INTRODUCTION

The islands of Ascension (7°56'S, 14°22'W) and Saint Helena (15°57'S, 5°43'W) are two small volcanic islands in the South Atlantic (Ascension: 88 km² and Saint Helena: 121 km²), located near the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (Ascension on the South American plate and Saint Helena on the African plate), whose origin is dated back to 5-6 million years (NIELSON & SIBBETT, 1996) and 11-14 million of years (BAKER, 1973) respectively. Ascension Island is separated from Africa by about 1600 km and 2300 from South America, while Saint Helena is about 2000 km from the African continent and more than 4000 km from South America. The distance between the two islands is 1290 km.

In recent years, the malacofauna of the Atlantic islands has been addressed in several works: This regards the Macaronesian islands of Cape Verde (ROLÁN, 2005), Canary Islands (NORDSIECK & GARCÍA-TALAVERA, 1979; HERNANDEZ ET AL. 2011), Selvagens (ALBUQUERQUE, BORGES & CALADO, 2009), Madeira (SEGERS, SWINNEN & DE PRINS, 2009), Azores (FRIAS MARTINS ET AL., 2009) or with Atlantic islands closer to the American continents such as the Bahamas (REDFERN, 2013), Curaçao, Aruba and Bonaire (DE JONG & COOMANS, 1988). Work has also been carried out on some specific groups of Molluscs such as Heterobranch sea slugs from Ascension Island (PADULA, WIRTZ & SCHRÖDL, 2014).

Regarding the family Pyramidellidae Gray, 1840 s.l., there is a large number of published works referring to the two Atlantic coasts. AARTSEN, GITTENBERGER & GOUD (1998, 2000), LYGRE & SCHANDER (2010), LYGRE ET AL. (2011), LYGRE, KONGSRUD & SCHANDER (2011), NOFRONI & SCHANDER (1994), PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1997, 1998, 1999a, b, 2000, 2001, 2002), PEÑAS, ROLÁN & SWINNEN (2014) and SCHANDER (1994) focus on the African coast while ABSALÃO, DOS SANTOS & DE OLIVERA (2003), PIMENTA (2012), PIMENTA & ABSALÃO (2001, 2004A, 2004B), PIMENTA, ABSALÃO &

MIYAJI (2009), PIMENTA, SANTOS & ABSALÃO (2008 and 2011) and GÜLLER & ZELAYA (2019) focus on the South American coast. To these studies we must add those carried out in Atlantic seamounts, such as PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999b) and PEÑAS ET AL. (2014).

To these recent studies, we should add the works carried out at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th on the African malacological fauna that, to a greater or lesser extent, dealt with the Family Pyramidellidae: BARTSCH (1915), DAUTZENBERG (1910, 1912), DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1906), SOWERBY III (1892), SMITH (1872, 1904), PALLARY (1922) or those referring to a particular island such as the cases of São Tomé (TOMLIN & SHACKLEFORD, 1915) or both islands of our study (SMITH, 1890a, b) and, more recently, Ascension (ROSEWATER, 1975).

In Smith's works, twelve species of Pyramidellidae are mentioned in Saint Helena (*Obeliscus dolabratus*, *Obeliscus sanctaehelena*, *Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio*, *Turbonilla haroldi*, *Turbonilla assimilians*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides*, *Turbonilla brachia*, *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima*, *Cingulina circinata*, *Cingulina (Mathilda) quadricarinata*, *Odostomia glaphira* and *Leucotina minuta* (SMITH, 1890a), but none from Ascension (SMITH, 1890b). ROSEWATER (1975) only mentioned *Pyramidella dolabrata*.

VOLCANIC ISLANDS AND COLONIZATION

Saint Helena and Ascension are two islands whose formation has taken place in the last 14 million years as a result of the volcanic activity of the mid-Atlantic ridge which accompanies the opening the Atlantic Ocean more than 100 million years ago (Fig. 1). At the time of their formation, the islands were already far enough from the African and American coastlines to make colonization by shallow-water marine species difficult.

Figure 1. Location of Ascension and Saint Helena islands and main marine currents (currents map reproduced from MULLER-KARGER *ET AL.* 2017).

Figura 1. Localización de las islas de Ascensión y Santa Elena y principales corrientes marinas (mapa de corrientes reproducido de MULLER-KARGER *ET AL.* 2017).

The shallow water species that colonize the oceanic islands arrive mainly in the form of planktonic larvae drifting in oceanic currents, but can also be transported through rafting (e.g. the transport of South African marine benthic invertebrates on *Laminaria*, ARNAUD, ARNAUD & LE LOEUFF, 1976). In the case of the Pyramidellidae, due to their ectoparasitic mode of life, colonization presents a double difficulty since they require prior colonization by a host species on which they can feed, or the presence of a suitable alternative host, something that hampers species dependent on a single host. After colonization, isolation favours allopatric speciation and as a consequence the appearance of endemic species.

Saint Helena and Ascension are located in the area of influence of the

Atlantic South-Equatorial Current driven by the southeast trade winds, coming in turn from the Benguela Current which goes up the western coast of Africa. Further north, the Equatorial Countercurrent pushes waters coming from the American coast in an easterly direction and when it reaches the African coasts it converges with the Guinea Current and directs its waters towards the south. In this way, with this current regime, it is to be expected that the planktonic larvae of coastal organisms that reach Saint Helena and Ascension have a preferentially African origin although it cannot be ruled out that they may have an American origin.

However, it must be taken into account that, after the formation of both islands, the circulation of marine currents, either due to climatic reasons

(such as the recent glacial periods) or tectonic reasons (for example, the formation of the Isthmus of Panama) may have changed, so that the colonizing species of these islands could have come from both continents.

On the other hand, it is well known that the insular biodiversity is less than that of the nearby continents and that factors such as island dimensions, geological age and proximity to the continent play an important role in it (MACARTHUR AND WILSON, 1967). That is why the recent geological age, the small area and the large distance from the continents of Saint Helena and Ascension are responsible for less biodiversity when compared to islands closer to the coast and larger, such as Cape Verde or the Canary Islands.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the material studied belongs to the F. Swinnen collection, the detail information of collectors given hereafter in each species entry. Samples have been collected from 42 sampling stations on Saint Helena, (between 1 and 90 m depth) and from 41 on Ascension (between 1 and 150 m depth). The material was separated using a stereomicroscope and photographed with SEM at the MNCN in Madrid and at the CACTI of the University of Vigo.

Taxonomic issues

In the Family Pyramidellidae, the specific determination and generic placement is an unsettled matter.- Despite this, a large number of species have been described (placed in turn in numerous genera) although, very often, poorly or from a few specimens, which makes their subsequent identification difficult. Such determinations, like those of our study, were usually based on characters of the shell (the only feasible in palaeontology for obvious reasons, the predominant ones from the historical point of view, and the only possible in numerous species of which the animal is unknown). Despite not seeming very

modern, conchological studies are still essential to form the necessary taxonomic reference framework that should serve as a reference for subsequent anatomical, genetic, ecological or other studies that may be undertaken. In our study we aimed not only to identify the different species, some new to science, but in some cases we had had to decide of their generic placement and for this we have followed the following criteria:

Specific determination: In the first place, the work of SMITH (1890a) has been taken as a reference, which has allowed us to identify most of these species. Some of them have been confirmed by studying the photographs of the syntypes from the Turton collection deposited at the NHMUK.

A second aspect that we have taken into consideration in the specific determination is the high degree of endemism, consequence of allopatric speciation associated with insularity. Those of Saint Helena and Ascension cannot be an exception.

The third aspect, logically, has been conditioned by the number of shells that we have been able to study of each species.

Taking this into account, we have opted for:

a) Keep the specific name of Smith whenever possible.

b) In the event that a species was present on both islands but some difference was detected, the Ascension one was considered "conferred".

c) In the species not recorded by Smith, it has been decided to use "cf." if there is a comparable specific reference in the nearby mainland coast.

d) Species with significantly differentiating morphological and/or habitat characteristics have been described as new. Those for which the comparable species were very distant geographically have also been considered new species.

Generic determination: In recent years, for systematic but also practical reasons, there is a tendency to recover historical genera and subgenera (elevat-

ing them to the generic category) in order to alleviate the specific overload of some genera (such as *Odostomia*, *Chrysalida* or *Turbonilla*). This criterion has been followed in this study, therefore many of Smith's original generic placements have been changed. The reasons will be explained for each specific case.

On the other hand, the importance of the study of the heterostrophic protoconch for the correct identification of Pyramidellidae has required the use of a pertinent terminology: protoconch are classified as types A, B and C following VAN AARTSEN (1987).

Subsequent authors essentially maintained this terminology which is also followed herein.

Abbreviations used

frg: fragment

j: juvenile

sh: empty shell (s)

spc: specimen (s) with soft part

leg: collector

ANSDU: Academy of Natural Sciences Drexel University (ANSP Philadelphia).

MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid.

NHMUK: Natural History Museum United Kingdom, London.

RBINS: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels

USNM: United States National Museum, Smithsonian Institution, Washington D. C.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Pyramidella dolabrata (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 2)

Original description: *Trochus dolabratus*: Linnaeus, 1758: 760.

Trochus dolabratus Linnaeus, 1758

Helix terebella O. F. Müller, 1774

Pyramidella terebellum (O. F. Müller, 1774)

Plotia lineata Röding, 1798

Urambella ballerina Laseron, 1959

Sayella micalii Peñas & Rolán, 1997

Tiberia micalii (Peñas & Rolán, 1997)

Type material: 4 syntypes in the Linnean Society of London (A-F0020181).

Material examined: syntypes (on photograph) and 11 juvenile shells and 6 fragments from 3 samples from Saint Helena and 3 adult or subadult shells, 11 juvenile shells and 17 fragments from 15 samples from the Ascension: SAINT HELENA • 11 sh (j) +1frg; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 frg; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; 2 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 4 frg; Black Rocks NR Thompsons Valley; -20 m; Leeann Henry leg. ASCENSION • 2 sh (j); China Wreck, Georgetown; 07°53'40.5"S, 14°25'28.2"W; -27 m; 25 May 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Comfortless Cove; 7° 54' 36.7"S, 14° 24' 11.9"W; 6.5-10.5 m; 14 Jul. 2015; Jerry Pierce leg. • 2 frg.; Comfortless Cove; -6 m; 1 Jan. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 2 frg; English Bay; -12 m; 5 Feb. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 frg; English Bay; -9 m; 8 Feb. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 3 frg; Ladies Loo; -17 m; 24 Jan. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 3 frg; Ladies Loo; -18 m; 12 May 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 5 sh (j); Ladies Loo; -20 m; 21 Feb. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 2 frg; One Hook; -10 m; 25 Apr. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh (j); One Hook; -20 m; 5 May 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 1 frg; One Hook; 4 Nov. 2015; Sarah Browning-Lee leg. • 1 frg; Red Rock; -27 m; 17 Dec. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 1 frg; Two Hooks; -18 m; 27 Nov. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh (j); Wiggan Pier; -13 m.; 1 Feb. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Wiggan Pier; -15 m.; 3 Feb. 2018; Sarah Browning-Lee leg.

Type locality: Not stated.

Description (based on material examined): Conical shell, relatively fragile, large for its family, reaching, in the

studied shells, 17 × 8 mm with eight whorls, not counting the first ones of the apex that are broken. Whorls with a flat-

tened convex profile with shallow suture. No kind of sculpture is observed. Aperture oval., Spiral folds visible inside the outer lip, in some shells (Fig. 2C). Small and deep umbilicus hidden by a columella with three folds (Fig. 2B), of which the upper one is more voluminous.

Protoconch type B tending to A, of 440 μm , with a wide, barely visible nucleus (Fig. 2E).

Colour yellowish-white with reddish spiral lines, beginning on the first whorls with a suprasutural line to which others are added as the shell grows. Of these, that located $\frac{3}{4}$ of the height of the suture is more intense and stands out (Figs. 2A, C).

Remarks: This is a variable species (hence its number of synonyms) and widely distributed. It has been reported from Japan (OKUTANI, 2000), the Philippines (DOLOROSA & DAGAN-GALON, 2014), the Red Sea (TRYON, 1886), the

Caribbean Sea and the American Atlantic coast (BENTHEM JUTTING (1925), SILVA MELLO (1990) and DE JONG & COOMANS (1988)) or for both continental and insular African Atlantic coasts (TRYON (1886), AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1998), PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1997) (as *Sayella micalii*), PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014) and ROLÁN (2005)). For Ascension Island it has been cited by ROSEWATER (1975) and for Saint Helena by SMITH (1890a).

In this study, only fragments and juveniles have been found in three points of Saint Helena, although all the juveniles (11) come from a single sampling station: Egg Island in debris at a depth of 29 m.

On Ascension Island the species appears to be more abundant than on Saint Helena as shells or fragments were found at 15 of the sampled points. 14 shells were found, three of them adults. Of these, two were found in Comfortless Cove (6.5-10.5 m).

Tiberia sanctaehelenae (E.A. Smith, 1890) (Figs. 3, 4, 19A)

Original description: *Obeliscus sanctaehelenae* E.A. Smith, 1890: 275, pl. 23 fig. 17.

Obeliscus sanctae-helenae E.A. Smith, 1890

Pyramidella sanctaehelenae (E.A. Smith, 1890)

Type material: 28 syntypes from the Turton collection deposited in NHMUK (ecatalogue 5605706) and 1 syntype in ANSDU (catalog 67884 collection of Sowerby G.B.).

Material examined (*Tiberia sanctaehelenae*): Syntypes (on photograph) and 32 adult or juvenile shells and 18 protoconchs in 8 samples: SAINT HELENA: • 18 sh (j); Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; 12 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 16 sh; Dawson; -90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 7 sh; Frontier Wreck; -22 m; 11 Jul. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; James Bay; -10 m; 22 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh (j); James Bay Mooring; -28 m; 8 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh (j); Papanui wreck; -12 m; 17 May. 2017; Leeann Henry, leg. • 1 sh; Papanui wreck; -11 m; 19 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry, leg.

Material examined (*Tiberia cf. sanctaehelenae*): 45 adult and juvenile shells, more than 100 protoconchs and several fragments in 5 samples: ASCENSION • 26 sh (15 j) + 4 frg; Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 4°25'59.4"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg. • 6 sh + 2 frg; Georgetown; 07°54'38.0"S, 14°26'39.2"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 3, Andy Richardson leg. • 1 sh; Grattan Seamount, 09°04'18.8"S, 12°48'41.7"W; -90 to -100 m; 25 Jan. 2018; Andy Richardson leg. • 11 sh; North Ascension Island; 07°52'35.1"S, 14°23'32"W; -150 m; 25 Feb. 2019; Andy Richardson leg. • >120 sh (j); SW Ascension Island, 07°58'00.0"S, 14°26'38.3"W; -150 m; 25 Feb. 2019; Andy Richardson leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena Island.

Description (based on the material examined): Shell conical with about seven whorls, up to 5.4 × 2 mm. Spire profile planoconvex with a shallow suture and

under which, in some shells, a faint sub-sutural keel can give the shell a slightly stepped profile (Figs. 3H, 4A, 4F). Shell surface smooth, without sculpture except

Figure 2. *Pyramidella dolabrata*. A, B: shell (17 mm) from Comfortless Cove, 6.5-10.5m (Ascension Island), and detail of its columellar folds; C: subadult shell (12.0 mm) from Wiggan Pier (Ascension Island), -15 m; D: juvenile shell from Long Ledge (Saint Helena), -19 m; E: protoconch of a shell from Ladies Loo (Ascension Island), -20 m.

Figura 2. *Pyramidella dolabrata*. A, B: *Concha* (17 mm) de Comfortless Cove, 6,5-10,5m (Isla de Ascensión), y detalle de sus pliegues columelares; C: *concha* subadulta (12,0 mm) de Wiggan Pier (Isla de Ascensión), -15 m; D: *concha* juvenil de Long Ledge (Santa Elena), -19 m; E: *protoconcha* de una *concha* de Ladies Loo (Isla de Ascensión), -20 m.

for orthocline growth lines (Figs. 3C, 4D). Aperture with three columellar folds, the upper one larger (Fig. 3E); the two lower folds barely perceptible in some shells (Figs. 3J, 4B). Inside the outer lip four lirae can be seen, inconspicuous in some shells (Figs. 3D, 3H, 4A, 4D). Both the columellar and labial folds usually located quite internally, so that they are more visible in those shells with a broken lip (Figs. 3C, D, 4D). Below the columella a broad umbilicus (Fig. 3J) can be seen in adult shells.

Colour dirty white with a more yellowish base. In fresh shells, a diffuse ochre-yellowish stain can be seen on the protoconch and a faint yellowish supra-sutural line on the teleoconch.

Protoconch type B tending to A, of 400 µm, in which the nucleus is not visible (Figs. 3F, 4G).

Remarks: SMITH (1890a: 275) described and figured *Obeliscus sanctaehelenae* in his work on Saint Helena Island. Our specimens from Saint Helena fit this description as well as the

photograph of the syntype, so their conspecificity seems clear. There seems to be considerable variability regarding the strength of the columellar folds, the internal dentition and the consistency of the shell, in such a way that the most consistent shells have stronger dentition and folds.

The shells of Ascension Island show some differences with respect to those of Saint Helena: they are slightly more cylindrical, clearly more fragile, grayish white in colour without yellowish tones and with the ochre stain of the protoconch more evident.

We have to consider that the revision of the genus *Tiberia* is still pending, surely due to the intrinsic difficulties of this genus (few differentiating morphological traits, scarcity of available material, wide geographical dispersion and presence mainly in deep waters). The WoRMS database includes (as of May 2022) twenty-three currently valid species belonging to the genus *Tiberia*. Eight of them were described before the species considered here, being *Tiberia minuscula* (Monterosato, 1880) the type species of the genus. APPOLLONI ET AL. (2018) provided a photograph of the type *Pyramidella* (*Tiberia*) *minuscula* from San Vito, Palermo (Sicily). Proof of the taxonomic difficulty of this group is that apart from certain possible chromatic differences, neither the size nor the appearance of *Pyramidella* (*Tiberia*) *minuscula* differs significantly from our species: (compare figure 27M in APPOL-

LONI ET AL. (2018) with Fig. 3H herein from Saint Helena or Fig. 4A from Ascension). It is therefore more appropriate to refer to it generically as *Tiberia* than as *Pyramidella*.

Regarding the *Tiberia* of our study, it should be noted that *Tiberia* cf. *sanctahelenae* has only been found in deeper samples from Ascension, but not in the shallowest samples. This contrasts with the presence of *Tiberia sanctahelenae* in both shallow and deep waters of Saint Helena. These bathymetric differences would seem to point to the possibility of two or more cryptic species. However, the comparative study of the populations of the *Tiberia* of Saint Helena and Ascension, although it has shown a certain degree of variability (especially referring to the strength of the shell and the columellar and labial dentitions), has not allowed to find differences significant enough to consider them different species. We therefore found preferable to refer to the Ascension species as *Tiberia* cf. *sanctahelenae* awaiting further studies to clarify the taxonomic position of both taxa.

It is also worth mentioning the similarity in terms of colour and consistency of the *Tiberia* of Ascension Island with *Tiberia apicifusca* van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998, a species of Cape Verde Islands from which it differs by being narrower and by having orthocone growth lines (opisthocline in *apicifusca*), although given the variability observed a more exhaustive comparison would be required.

Odostomella truncatelloides (E.A. Smith, 1890) n. comb. (Figs. 5, 19C, D)

Original description: *Turbonilla truncatelloides* E.A. Smith, 1890: 276, pl. 23 fig. 20.
Turbonilla truncatelloides E.A. Smith, 1890

(Right page) Figure 3. *Tiberia sanctahelenae* (Saint Helena Island). A: original drawing of *Tiberia sanctahelenae* (in SMITH, 1890a); B: syntype, ANSDU 67884 (5.2 mm); C: shell (4.7 mm) from James Bay, -10 m; D, E: shell (3.8 mm) from Frontier Wreck, -22 m and detail of columellar folds and internal dentition; F: protoconch of a shell from Dawson, -90 m; G: shell (4.3 mm), same locality; H-J: shell (3.4 mm), same locality, protoconch and umbilical detail; K: detail of the columellar folds, same locality.

Figura 3. *Tiberia sanctaehelenae* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *Tiberia sanctaehelenae* (en SMITH, 1890a); B: sintipo, ANSDU 67884 (5,2 mm); C: concha (4,7 mm) de James Bay, -10 m; D, E: concha (3,8 mm) de Frontier Wreck, -22 m y detalle de pliegues columelares y dentición interna; F: protoconcha de una concha de Dawson, -90 m; G: concha (4,3 mm), misma localidad; H-J: concha (3,4 mm), misma localidad, protoconcha y detalle del ombligo; K: detalle de los pliegues columelares, misma localidad.

Figure 4. *Tiberia* cf. *sanctaehelenaе* (Ascension Island). A-C: shell (3.4 mm) from SW Ascension Island, 7°58,000'S, 14°26,639'W, -150 m, detail of the columella and protoconch; D-G: shell (3.3 mm) from North Ascension Island; 7°52,585'S, 14°23,533'W, -150 m, detail of the columellar fold, microsculpture and protoconch.

Figura 4. *Tiberia* cf. *sanctaehelenaе* (Isla de Ascensión). A-C: concha (3,4 mm) de SO de Isla de Ascensión, 7°58,000'S, 14°26,639'W, 150 m, detalle de la columella y de su protoconcha; D-G: concha (3,3 mm) del Norte de Isla de Ascensión, 7°52,585'S, 14°23,533'W, -150 m, detalle del pliegue columelar, microescultura y protoconcha.

Type material: 5 syntypes from the Turton collection deposited in NHMUK (catalogue number 5605712) and 1 more syntype in The Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia (catalogue 67919 from Sowerby collection).

Material examined: Syntypes (photograph) and 3 shells (2 juveniles from Saint Helena and one protoconch from Ascension): SAINT HELENA • 2 sh (j); Dawson; -90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. ASCENSION (*O.* cf. *truncatelloides*) • 1 sh (j); Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena Island.

Figure 5. *Odostomella truncatelloides* (Saint Helena). A: original drawing of *Turbonilla truncatelloides* (in SMITH, 1890a); B, C: shell (2.4 mm) from Dawson, -90 m, and detail of its columellar fold; D, E: view of the protoconch, same locality; F: *Odostomella cf. truncatelloides* (Ascension Island), protoconch of a shell from Georgetown station 2, 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W, -130 m.

Figura 5. *Odostomella truncatelloides* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *Turbonilla truncatelloides* (en SMITH, 1890a); B, C: concha (2,4 mm) de Dawson, 90 m, y detalle de su pliegue columelar; D, E: vista de la protoconcha, misma localidad; F: *Odostomella cf. truncatelloides* (Isla de Ascensión), protoconcha de una concha de Georgetown station 2, 07°53'30,3"S, 14°25'59,4"W, -130 m.

Description: SMITH (1890: 276) illustrated and described *Turbonilla truncatelloides* in his work on the Island of Saint Helena. Although his illustration is not precise enough, the few shells studied essentially coincide with this description, as well as some of its syntypes (compare Figs. 5B, 19D), so we consider that our shells are conspecific. The juvenile shell studied by us has almost six whorls, 2.4 mm in height, a stepped profile (Fig. 5B) and a columellar fold (Fig. 5C). It has a type B protoconch with a width of 300 µm (Figs. 5D, E). Its colour is whitish and it has a yellowish line in the middle of the whorl.

Remarks: It is clear that the characteristics of this species fit better with the genus *Odostomella* than with *Turbonilla*, which is why we will refer to it as *Odostomella truncatelloides*.

On Saint Helena it has only been found at Dawson at a depth of 90 metres. On Ascension, a juvenile has also been found

in deep water (130 m) and due the scarce material and its size, we have preferred, for geographical reasons, to refer to it as *O. cf. truncatelloides*.

The size of *O. truncatelloides* makes it only comparable to *O. bicincta* since other *Odostomella* present in West or South Africa such as *O. africana*, *O. farica* and *O. doliolum*, are smaller and do not usually exceed 2 mm.

Odostomella bicincta has a more pupoid and less stepped profile than *O. truncatelloides*. In addition, its ribs are more numerous, somewhat curved and tend to be opisthoclinal while they are straight and orthoclinal in *O. truncatelloides*.

Odostomella cf. africana Schander, 1994 (in PEÑAS *ET AL.* (2014), p.131, figs. 9A-B) from Lagoa Azul (Santo Tomé), with almost five whorls, reaches 2.23 mm in height, has straight and orthoclinal ribs, a strong columellar fold and a 340 µm wide protoconch, characters

which distance it from the original description of *O. africana* and approximate *O. truncatelloides*, from which it

still differs by having a more stepped profile, at least in the first whorls, and a somewhat smaller protoconch (320 µm).

Odostomella cf. fonteini (De Jong & Coomans, 1988) (Fig. 6)

Original description: *Turbonilla fonteini* De Jong & Coomans, 1988: 131, pl. 20 fig. 679.

Type material: Holotype of *Turbonilla fonteini* In Zoologisch Museum, Amsterdam, ZMA 3.87.111. **Material examined:** Photographs of the holotype *Turbonilla fonteini* (in DE JONG & COOMANS (1988) and PIMENTA ET AL. (2009)) and 23 shells in ten samples: ASCENSION • 1 sh; Eddies Gullies, in detritus under large rock reef; -15.5 m; 7 Nov. 2015; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 7 sh; English Bay; -12 m; in sand; 5 Feb. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; English Bay; 7°53'25.42"S, 14°22'50.24"W; -9 m; below big arches; 11 Nov. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 6 sh; Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg. • 2 sh; Georgetown; 07°54'38.0"S, 14°26'39.2"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 3, Andy Richardson leg. • 1 sh; Georgetown, 07°55'12.7"S, 14°26'15.8"W; -60 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 4, Andy Richardson leg. • 1 sh; North Point; -23 m sandy seabed next to steep rock reef face; 11 Mar. 2017; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; One Hook; -10 m; in detritus; 25 Apr. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh; One Hook; -17 m; in detritus; 25 Apr. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; SW Ascension Island, 07°58'00.0"S, 14°26'38.3"W; -150 m; 25 Feb. 2019; Fishing vessel "Extractor", Andy Richardson leg. **Type locality:** Bonaire, West Indies.

Description: Shell very small, pupoid that, with four whorls, up to 1.5 × 0.6 mm. Spire with flat profile and shallow suture. Ribs straight, slightly prosocline, as wide as their interspaces and somewhat bulging in their upper part, forming a slight subsutural rim (Fig. 6H). About 18 ribs on the last whorl, reaching the base of the shell and curved below the callosity of the inner lip (Figs. 6A, F). Weak spiral grooves on the entire surface of the shell (Fig. 6E). Aperture almond-shaped, narrower at the top, with a bulge at the insertion point of the upper lip (Fig. 6G). Very weak and internal columellar fold (Fig. 6B).

Protoconch type B, 325 µm wide.

Colour generally purple although there are also yellowish shells.

Remarks: DE JONG AND COOMANS (1988) described *Odostomella fonteini* (as *Turbonilla fonteini*) from shells from Bonaire

and Aruba. Subsequently PIMENTA ET AL. (2009) recombined the specific name as *Odostomella fonteini* and extended its distribution to the Brazilian coasts. In the absence of a physical comparison of the specimens, we believe that the data and photographs provided by these authors are sufficient to consider the possible conspecificity with our species, which we refer to as *O. cf. fonteini* for its insularity.

Odostomella cf. fonteini has been found at depths between 9 and 150 meters, as was also *O. fonteini* on the American coasts, although on Ascension the specimens from deeper waters are smaller than those from surface waters and are yellowish in colour although they maintain their purple protoconch.

Odostomella farica (Bartsch, 1915) is a species of similar size from South Africa but is white with brown bands and has more orthocline axial ribs.

(Right page) Figure 6. *Odostomella cf. fonteini* (Ascension Island). A, B: shell (1.4 mm) from English Bay, 7°53'25.42"S, 14°22'50.24"W, -12 m and detail of the outer lip insertion; C-E: shell (1.3 mm) from English Bay, -12 m, protoconch and detail of microsculpture of the shell; F-I: shell (1.2 mm) from English Bay, -12 m and detail of aperture, outer lip insertion and protoconch; J, K: shell (1.3 mm) from Georgetown station 2, 7°53.505'S, 14°25.990'W, 130 m, and protoconch.

Figura 6. *Odostomella cf. fonteini* (Isla de Ascensión). A, B: concha (1,4 mm) de English Bay, 7°53'25,42"S, 14°22'50,24"W, -12 m) y detalle de la inserción del labio externo; C-E: concha (1,3 mm) de English Bay, -12 m, protoconcha y detalle de la microestructura de la concha; F-I: concha (1,2 mm) de English Bay, -12 m y detalle de la apertura, inserción del labio externo y protoconcha; J, K: protoconcha y concha (1,3 mm) de Georgetown estación 2, 7°53,505'S, 14°25,990'W, 130 m.

Cingulina boirai n. sp. (Fig. 7)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:53469955-1453-4176-896D-0EF1788EFE41

Cingulina circinata A. Adams, 1860 (misidentification in SMITH, 1890a).

Type material and type locality: *Holotype*. SAINT HELENA • 1 sh; Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole in cave entrance; 15°54'40"S, 5°41'17"W; -15 m; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. 0428/Q323; RBINS, Brussels, n° I.G. 34553 (MT.3948). *Paratypes*. SAINT HELENA • 3 sh; same data as holotype; MNCN n° 15.05/200204 • 3 sh; same data as holotype; MNHN-IM-2022-11298 • 1 sh; same data as holotype; private collection of F. Swinnen.

Other material examined: 264 shells, adults and juveniles, in 17 samples: SAINT HELENA • 5 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; 26 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Bennetts Point towards Lady's Chair W: -23 m; sand; 15 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 4 sh; Bird Island; -12 m; in detritus in cave-tunnel; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 8 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; under large boulders; 7 Oct. 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 12 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; under large boulders; 7 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 18 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; under large boulders; 7 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 80 sh (60 j); Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole; 15°54'40", 5°41'17"W; -15 m; at cave entrance; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 8 sh; Bouy's Hole; -10 m; in sand; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 25 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; in detritus; 13 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 3 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -10 m; inside a cave; 30 Jul. 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Long Ledge East; -12 m; low overhang; 22 May 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 22 sh; Long Ledge East; -12 m; 22 May 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 18 sh; Merriman Island; 15°54'43"S, 5°40'10"W; -16 m; in sand; 16 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 9 sh; Merriman Point; -10 m; under ledge; 8 Aug. 2015; Leeann Henry & Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Papanui wreck, close Jamestown; -11 m; base of wreck; 10 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 25 sh; Red Island; -12 m; bedrock overhangs; 30 Dec. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 9 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; bedrock and boulders; 2 May 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 14 sh; Ruperts Jetty; -11 m; in detritus; 5 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg.

Etyymology: Dedicated to "Capità Boira", literary alter ego of Tono Fornés, biologist, poet and passionate about the sea, friend and collaborator in the collection of samples of the first author.

Description: Shell high, conical, with just over seven whorls, not counting those of its protoconch, up to 3.8×1.4 mm. Whorls with flattened convex profile and shallow suture, concealed between the upper spiral cord and the lower groove of each whorl.

Dominant spiral sculpture formed by three very prominent smooth spiral cords, of which the upper one is usually narrower and the central one is wider, although it becomes equal to the lower one as the shell grows (Fig. 7B). The upper cord coincides with the suture while the lower cord is a little above the suture, leaving below a canaliculated space in which the upper part of a fourth cord can occasionally be perceived, which is hidden as the shell grows (Fig. 7F). The interspaces, concave and deep, are narrower than the cords and in their interior some narrow axial lamellae can be seen that can occasionally extend over the cords themselves (Figs. 7B, C, I).

The base of the shell is smooth except for the presence of a weak but evident spiral groove and because there the growth lines become somewhat more visible (Fig. 7D). The aperture is oval, the columella is somewhat inclined and has a very slight curvature. It lacks navel and columellar dentition.

Protoconch of type A with the upper part of its nucleus barely visible. The protoconch of the specimen studied was 230 μ m wide (Figs. 7H-J).

Remarks: Arthur ADAMS (1860) described the genus *Cingulina* with *C. circinata* from Japan and China as its type species. Since then, more than twenty species ascribed to this genus have been described (24 in the WoRMS database in June 2022) but for many of them lack descriptive details, illustrations or photographs detailed enough to determine them unequivocally. Pending a review of the genus we have compared our species with those species of

Figure 7. *Cingulina boirai* n. sp. A-D: shell (3.3 mm) from Red Island, -12 m and different details of its sculpture; E, F: shell (3.8 mm) from Ruperts Jetty, -11 m and detail of its suture; G: holotype (3.8 mm) from Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole, -15 m; H-J: different views of the protoconch, shell from Red Island, -12 m.

Figura 7. Cingulina boirai n. sp. A-D: concha (3,3 mm) de Red Island, -12 m y distintos detalles de su escultura; E, F: concha (3,8 mm) de Ruperts Jetty, -11 m y detalle de su sutura; G: holotipo (3,8 mm) de Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole, -15 m; H-J: distintas vistas de la protoconcha, concha de Red Island, -12 m.

Cingulina that have either been frequently cited in recent literature or are close geographically, such as *C. circinata*, *C. cingulata*, *C. isseli* and *C. acutilirata*. It will also be compared with the South African *Polyspirella trachealis*.

Cingulina circinata A. Adams 1860 is the type species and was originally described from the China Sea and Japan. SOWERBY III (1892) indicated its presence in Port Elizabeth (South Africa) and commented on the difficulty of distinguishing it from Asian specimens. Smith himself cited *C. circinata* for St. Helena. On the other hand GOULD (1861) described *Chemnitzia circumdata* from shells collected by the United States North Pacific Exploring Expedition in Sydney (Australia). ODÉ (1998), without providing data, considers *Chemnitzia circumdata* as a possible synonym of *C. circinata*. If this were verified, *C. circinata* would be a species with an extensive range extend from China and Japan to Australia and South Africa.

However, there are some drawbacks. The original description of *C. circinata* A. Adams, 1860 is not accompanied by a figure and may apply to any species of *Cingulina*. For this reason, all subsequent references to *C. circinata* until HIGO ET AL. (2001) published the photograph of a possible syntype, should be taken with caution. This reservation applies to Smith's record of *C. circinata* from Saint Helena. *Cingulina circinata* from Japan (with 11 whorls and 12 mm height) is larger than the Saint Helena *Cingulina* (8 whorls and 5 mm height). In addition, its spiral cords are flatter, they are closer together and the basal sculpture is different. This, together with the great distance that separates them, makes them clearly distinct species.

Cingulina cingulata (Dunker, 1860), a species also present in Japan, is best known for being well represented in recent literature e.g. OKUTANI (2000) and KANTOR & SYSOEV (2006). It differs from *Cingulina boirai* n. sp. in having five basal cords.

Cingulina isseli (Tryon, 1886) is a Red Sea species found also in the Mediter-

ranean through Lessepsian migration. It is redescribed and illustrated in AARTSEN & CARROZZA (1983). It is a very similar species that differs by having a more cyrtoconoid profile and a width of the spiral cords more regular than our species.

Cingulina acutilirata G. B. Sowerby III, 1892 was described from Port Elizabeth (South Africa) with the indication that it was distinguished from *C. circinata* by the sharpness of its crests and the absence of interstitial crenulation, something that would also distinguish it from our species.

In order to refine the taxonomy of the African Pyramidellids, AARTSEN & CORGAN (1996) considered the taxon *Polyspirella* Carpenter, 1861 to have a generic value. This genus includes four species and *Polyspirella trachealis* is the type species. *Chemnitzia (Polyspirella) trachealis* was described by GOULD (1861) from specimens collected in South Africa (Cape of Good Hope and False Bay). Gould's description of this species is not very detailed but BARTSCH (1915) expanded on it, naming it *Turbonilla (Cingula) trachealis*. We do not believe that the characters of this species are significant enough to consider it a separate genus from *Cingulina* A. Adams 1860, so we prefer to refer to it as *Cingulina trachealis*.

Bartsch indicated that the spiral cords of *T. (C.) trachealis* are twice as wide as their interspaces and that from the fourth whorl onwards, part of a fourth spiral cord is visible on the suture. In *Cingulina boirai* n. sp. the interspaces are more than half the width of the cords and the fourth cord appears later, and only occasionally in a few shells. Also, at the base of the shell of *Cingulina boirai* n. sp., there is a groove that BARTSCH (1915) did not mention in *T. (C.) trachealis*. Without being able to physically compare both species, we consider that, for biogeographic reasons, these small morphological differences are sufficient to justify a different species.

On Saint Helena it has been one of the most abundant species. 264 speci-

mens from 15 stations have been studied. It has turned out to be especially abundant in the Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole station at the entrance of a cave 15 m deep where

about 80 adults and juvenile shells have been found. It has also been abundant under large rocks 7 meters deep in Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay where 38 shells were found.

Miralda verhaeghei n.sp. (Fig. 8)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2FF09151-2BDA-4A36-AD86-284BEB29D27E

Type material and type locality: *Holotype*. SAINT HELENA • 1 sh; Ruperts Bay, in detritus; 15°55'03"S, 5°42'42"W; -11 m; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. 170425/Q318; RBINS, Brussels n° I.G. 34553 (MT.3949). *Paratypes*. SAINT HELENA • 3 sh; Egg Island, bedrock and boulders; -8 m; 20 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg., cod. 170420/Q311; private collection of F. Swinnen • 2 shells, Bird Island, in cave tunnel; -12 m; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg.; MNCN n° 15.05/200203P • 2 shells, Bird Island, in cave tunnel; -12 m; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg.; MNHN-IM-2022-11297.

Material examined: The type material (8 shells) and 20 more shells, adults and juveniles, in 14 samples: SAINT HELENA • 2 j; Bedgellet Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; in sand; 12 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Bend Island; -17 m; in sand under bedrock ledge; 16 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Bennetts Point towards Lady's Chair W; -23 m; sand; 15 Mar. 2014; J. Brown leg. • 1 sh; Black Rocks, Thompsons Valley; -20 m; in a cave; 15 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 j; Buoy's Hole/Cavalley Hole; 15°54'40", 5°41'17"W; -15 m; at a cave entrance; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 j; Buoy's Hole; -10 m; in sand; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Cat Island; -11 m; near large boulders; 31 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry, leg. • 1 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; in detritus; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; in detritus; 13 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 4 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; in sand; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Red Rock Cave, near Cat Island; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; in detritus; 9 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown, leg. • 1 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; in detritus; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg.

Etymology: Named after Yves Verhaeghe, a friend for more than 30 years of the second author.

Description: Shell solid, white, conical, 2.5 × 1.1 mm in the holotype with almost five whorls. Spire with flat profile, with a canalculated suture. Three strong, flat spiral cords on each whorl, separated by deep interspaces; the two upper cords crossed by prosocline ribs giving both of them a tuberculate appearance (stronger on the upper cord; Fig. 8D). Basal cord smooth. Fine prosocline lamellae in the interspaces and also, although more faintly, on the cords, coincident with the growth lines (Figs. 8D, E). Last whorl with another flat cord at the level of the outer lip insertion, one more, somewhat narrower, at the base of the shell and finally a third, very weak cord bordering the columella. Aperture oval with a slightly crenulated outer lip and a small but evident, slightly internal tooth on the columella (Fig. 8H), much more visible on shells with a broken aperture. Helmet-shaped type B protoconch, 250 µm wide (Fig. 8G).

Remarks: *Miralda protogalea* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 is a species from Pacific islands of Vanuatu, Solomon and Fiji, which has minimal differences with our species. It is smaller (with almost the same number of whorls, the holotype of *M. protogalea* measures 1.85 × 0.87 mm compared to 2.5 × 1.1 mm of that of *Miralda verhaeghei* (Fig. 8A)). In addition, the central spiral cord of *Miralda verhaeghei* it is less tuberculate than that of *M. protogalea*. Finally, our species has been found in shallower waters than *M. protogalea* (collected at depths greater than 100 m). Considering that the genus has not been reviewed exhaustively and, despite the few morphological differences, it has seemed more convenient for biogeographical reasons, given the insularity and the enormous distance that separates them, to consider them different species. Accepting conspecificity would imply accepting a distribution area that is difficult to inter-

Figure 8. *Miralda verhaeghei* n. sp. A: holotipo (2,5 mm) from Ruperts Bay, -11 m; B-E: shell (1,9 mm) from Papanui wreck, -12 m, protoconch and details of sculpture of the teleoconch; F, G: view of the apex and its protoconch, same locality; H: base of the shell and columellar tooth, same locality.

Figura 8. Miralda verhaeghei n. sp. A: holotipo (2,5 mm) de Ruperts Bay, -11 m; B-E: concha (1,9 mm) de Papanui wreck, -12 m, protoconcha y detalles de la escultura de la teleoconcha, F, G: vista del ápice y de su protoconcha, misma localidad; H: base de la concha y diente columelar, misma localidad.

pret, for which reason we consider our species to be endemic to Saint Helena.

It does not seem to be very abundant but it does appear frequently in the

samples. In fact, the 28 shells studied appeared in 14 stations. The largest number of specimens (4) was found on sand, at a depth of 12 m at Papanui wreck.

Menestho minuta (E.A. Smith, 1890) n. comb. (Figs. 9, 19H, I)

Original description: *Leucotina minuta* E.A. Smith, 1890: 298, pl. 24 fig. 9.

Leucotina minuta E.A. Smith, 1890

Type material: 19 syntypes in NHMUK (ecatalogue 5605713, col. Turton) and 2 syntypes in The Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia (cat: 67872, col. G.B. Sowerby).

Material examined: 19 syntypes (photograph), and 4 specimens and 71 shells in 17 samples: SAINT HELENA • 5 sh; Bend Island; -17 m; under bedrock ledge; 16 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 9 sh; Bennetts Point towards Lady's Chair; -23 m; sand; 15 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Billy May's Revenge; -12 m; 12 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 4 spcs; Bird Island; -12 m; in detritus, in cave-tunnel; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Black Rocks NR Thompsons Valley; -20 m; 2 Oct. 2012; Leeann Henry leg. • 5 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; under large boulders; 7 Oct. 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 6 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; 7 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 7 sh; Cat Island; -11 m; near large boulders; 31 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 14 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 7 sh; Lighter Rock; 15°57'18"S, 5°45'43.2"W; -26 m; 12 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -10 m; inside a cave; 30 Jul. 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -12 m; low overhang; 22 May 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 4 sh; Merriman Point; -10 m; under ledge; 8 Aug. 2015; Leeann Henry & Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; in sand; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 2 sh; Peaked Island; -20 m; cave entrance; 9 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 5 sh; Red Island, bedrock overhangs; -12 m; 30 Dec. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Ruperts Bay, in detritus; -11 m; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena Island.

Description: Shell white, oval, with four whorls, up to 2.2 × 0.9 mm. Profile of whorls convex with a moderately deep suture. Spiral sculpture formed by flat cords, slightly elevated, of irregular width, generally wider than their interspaces (Fig. 9H). In the last whorl there are fifteen cords, of which seven or eight are above the apertural insertion. At the base of the shell, the cords usually merge, disappearing the interspaces. Interspaces shallow with numerous prosocline lamellae inside (Fig. 9H). Growth lines somewhat sigmoid and also prosocline. Aperture oval. Columella with a faint tooth located quite internally, not easy to see in some shells (Figs. 9B-D).

Protoconch of type B, 300 µm wide, strongly sculptured by spiral cords separated by deep grooves in which numerous axial lamellae can be seen (Fig. 9J).

Remarks: The existence of a certain morphological variability between more oval ($h/a=1.9$) or more cylindrical ($h/a=2.3$) shells has been verified (Figs. 9G, I).

Smith's description of this species and its illustration, which correspond to the syntype (Fig. 19I), fundamentally fit the shells that have been studied.

Seventy five shells from 16 stations have been studied, therefore this is a fairly abundant and well-distributed species. The largest number of specimens (14) were found in debris at a depth of 29 m on Egg Island.

As it is logical, in the absence of morphological or genetic studies of the animal that systematically place a certain species, we have to settle for a conchological study (which, on the other hand, is the only feasible one in paleontological studies) to generically place the species and provide a starting point for further research. Thus, *Leucotina minuta* E.A. Smith is considered at present to be a taxon of doubtful placement (*taxon inquirendum* in WoRMS database).

Several genera of Pyramidelloidea are characterized by conical shells with low, flat spiral ornamentation separated by shallow grooves. Some of these genera belong to the family Pyramidellidae: *Menestho* Møller, 1842 (type: *Turbo albulus* Fabricius, 1780), *Evalea* A. Adams 1860 (type: *Odostomia elegans* A. Adams 1860), *Iolaea* A. Adams 1860 (type: *Iole scitula* A. Adams 1860), *Odetta* de Folin, 1870 (type: *Odetta sulcata*, de Folin, 1870), and *Noemiamea* de Folin, 1866 (type: *Noemia valida* de Folin, 1872 = *Noemiamea dolioliformis* (Jeffreys,

1848)) and others in the family Amathidae: *Monotygma* G. B. Sowerby II 1839 (type: *Monotygma striata* Gray, 1847), and *Leucotina* A. Adams, 1860 (type *Leucotina niphonensis* A. Adams, 1860 = *Leucotina casta* (A. Adams, 1853)).

In the case of the genera of the Family Amathidae (*Leucotina* and *Monotygma*) the shape of the inner lip is different from that of the Pyramidellidae (the transition from the columella to the (more inflated) parietal wall is less smooth). Moreover, the comparison of *L. minuta* with *L. casta* (description and photographs in HORI & TSUCHIDA (1995) (as *L. dianae*)) shows important differences that prevent us from considering them congeneric. Unless anatomical or genetic studies may indicate otherwise, we consider *L. minuta* closer to family Pyramidellidae than to the family Amathidae.

DE FOLIN (1870) differentiated *Odetta* from *Noemiamea* by the absence or presence of axial ornamentation (present in *Noemiamea* and absent in *Odetta*). *Odetta sulcata* (photographed in AARTSEN ET AL. (1998: figs. 10, 13 and 54) has an A-type protoconch, a ribbed suture and spiral cords so flat and close together that their interspaces are barely visible. *Noemiamea dolioliformis* have an umbilicated shell, A-type protoconch and spiral cords (on which a very weak axial ornamentation is arranged) close together. We do not think *L. minuta* fits well into these two genera.

DALL & BARTSCH, 1909 proposed *Iolaea*, *Menestho* and *Evalea* as subgenera of *Odostomia* (now considered with generic value). The first two have axial sculpture reduced to mere threads in their interspaces, unlike in *Evalea*. The presence of an umbilicus in *Iolaea* would separate it from *Menestho*.

Menestho Møller has the type species *Menestho albula* (Fabricius, 1866).

Although Fabricius specimens have not been studied, we examined photographs of an Icelandic shell (WARÉN (1991: fig. 27F) that he considers identical to Møller's. In this shell, there is a weak axial ornamentation in the interspaces of the spiral cords. Although *M. albula* apparently lacks a tooth on the inner lip we consider that our *L. minuta* agrees better with this genus that has become a catch-all for any odostomiine with spiral cords or grooves and without axial sculpture. This has been the case with other recently described species such as *Menestho patagonica* or *M. beaglensis* (DI LUCA, GÜLLER & ZELAYA, 2021) that also have a small internal protrusion similar to the small internal tooth of our species. This same criterion could be applied to other species from the coast of West Africa very similar to ours such as *Leucotina elongata*, *L. lilyae* and *L. puncturata*.

One of the most peculiar characteristics of our species is the possession of a strongly sculptured protoconch. This characteristic is not common in the Pyramidellidae, unlike many Rissoidae genera such as *Alvania*, *Manzonina* or *Crisilla*. Some species of Pyramidellidae in which we can find this character are *Chrysallida verdensis*, *C. canariensis*, *C. minutissima*, *Parthenina moolenbeeki*, *Odostomia brandhorsti*, *Odetta dekleini* or *Menestho beermanae*. Regardless of whether later studies relocate these species to other genera, what seems to emerge is that the sculptured protoconch is the result of an evolutionary convergence that has appeared on several occasions in different families of Gastropods and also in different genera within the Pyramidellidae family, that could be related with the evolutionary advantage of a low dispersive capacity of the larval phase in limited distribution areas such as islands.

(Right page) Figure 9. *Menestho minuta* (Saint Helena). A: original drawing of *Leucotina minuta* (in SMITH, 1890a); B, C: shell (1.7 mm) from Egg Island, -29 m and detail of columellar tooth; D: shell (1.9 mm) from Cat Island, -11 m; E, F: shell (1.3 mm) from Cat Island, -11 m, and protoconch; G, H: shell (1.7 mm) from Egg Island, -29 m and detail of its microsculpture; I: shell (2.2 mm) from Cat Island, -11 m; J: apical view of a protoconch from Egg Island, -29 m.

Figura 9. *Menestho minuta* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *Leucotina minuta* (en SMITH, 1890a); B, C: concha (1,7 mm) de Egg Island, -29 m y detalle del diente columelar; D: concha (1,9 mm) de Cat Island, -11 m; E, F: concha (1,3 mm) de Cat Island, -11 m y protoconcha; G, H: concha (1,7 mm) de Egg Island, -29 m y detalle de su microescultura; I: concha (2,2 mm) de Cat Island, -11 m; J: vista apical de una protoconcha de Egg Island, -29 m.

Pyrgiscus haroldi (E.A. Smith, 1890) (Figs. 10 A-H, 19E)

Original description: *Turbonilla haroldi*, E.A. Smith, 1890: 275, pl. 23 fig. 18.

Type material: 20 Syntypes from the Turton Collection (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605711) and 2 Syntypes (col. G.B. Sowerby, cat. 67924) at The Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia.

Material examined: 20 syntypes (photograph) and 204 shells in 25 samples of 24 stations: SAINT HELENA • 3 sh; Approaching Young's Valley; 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.6"W; -7 m; 1 Mar. 2014; J. Brown leg. • 3 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'45.6"S, 5°45'18"W; -5 m; 7 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 6 sh; Bennetts Point towards Lady's Chair; -23 m; 15 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Bird Shit towards Banks; 15°54'43.2"S, 5°43'32.4"W; 22 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 18 sh; Black Rocks NR Thompsons Valley; -20 m; 15 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 40 sh; Bouy's Hole / Cavalley Hole; 15°54'40", 5°41'17"W; -15 m; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh; Bouy's Hole; -10 m; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Dawson; -90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 10 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh; Egg Island; 15°58'13"S, 5°46'14"W; -8 m; 20 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 9 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; 13 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Horse Pasture Point; -16 m; 25 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Lighter Rock; 15°57'18"S, 5°45'43.2"W; -26 m; 12 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 4 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 5 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 7 sh; Long Ledge; -19 m; 2 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 17 sh; Long Ledge; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Near Artificial reef; 15°55'33.6"S, 5°43'44.4"W; -28 m; 28 Jun. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 27 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 8 sh; Red Island; 15°56'34"S, 5°44'31.2"W; -12 m; 10 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 7 sh; Red Island; -12 m; 30 Dec. 2015; Leeann Henry, leg. • 1 sh; Red Island in Long Ledge; -12 m; 19 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Red Rock, Cave near Cat Island; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; 9 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 5 sh; Romans reef; -9 m; 9 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; 2 May. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 30 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh. Approaching Young's Valley (Saint Helena) 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.6"W; -7 m; in detritus; 1 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. ASCENSION: • 1 eroded shell, j (*Pyrgiscus* sp. (Figs. 10I, J)); North Ascension Island; 07°52'35.1"S, 14°23'32"W; -150 m; 25 Feb. 2019; Fishing vessel "Extractor", Andy Richardson leg. **Type locality:** Saint Helena Island.

Description: Shell tall, cyrtoconoid, with six whorls not counting the protoconch, up to 2.5 × 0.8 mm. Profile of whorls plano-convex, occasionally with a very faint subsutural depression. Suture shallow but with an incipient shelf, only visible at high magnification and not enough to give the shell a stepped profile.

Axial sculpture formed by ribs (around 16 in the last whorl), orthocline or slightly opisthocline, straight or slightly curved, equal to or somewhat narrower than their interspaces (Fig. 10E). Spiral sculpture formed by spiral cordlets visible between the ribs, some-

what narrower than their interspaces and fairly equidistant (Fig. 10E). On the last whorl, at the level of the outer lip insertion, a slightly wider spiral cord delimits an upper zone in which there are eight to ten cords weakening towards the suture, leaving a subsutural strip free of them, and a lower zone in which the ribs fade and the cords become more closely set across the base, giving the base a striated appearance (Fig. 10D). Aperture oval, narrow at the top. Inner lip with a faint, very internal, barely visible fold.

Protoconch with a width of 240 μm, of type B, with the nucleus partially visible.

(Right page) Figure 10. A-H. *Pyrgiscus haroldi*, (Saint Helena). A: original drawing as *Turbonilla haroldi* (in SMITH, 1890a); B-E: shell (2.5 mm) from Long Ledge, protoconch, detail of outer lip attachment and microsculpture of the teleoconch; F: shell (2.3 mm) from Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole; G, H: protoconchs from the same locality. I, J. *Pyrgiscus* sp. (1.5 mm) from North Ascension Island; 7°52.585'S, 14°23.533'W, 150 m, shell and detail of its microsculpture.

Figura 10. A-H. *Pyrgiscus haroldi*, (Santa Elena) A: dibujo original de *Turbonilla haroldi* (en SMITH, 1890a); B-E: concha (2,5 mm) de Long Ledge, protoconcha, detalle de la inserción del labio externo y de la microcultura de la teleconcha; F: concha (2,3 mm) de Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole; G, H: protoconchas de la misma localidad. I, J. *Pyrgiscus* sp. (1,5 mm) del Norte de Isla de Ascención, 7°52,585'S, 14°23,533'W, 150 m, concha y detalle de su microcultura.

The shell is transparent, yellowish or whitish.

Remarks: Although Smith's drawing is inaccurate, his description essentially coincides with our species, which in turn fits better in the genus *Pyrgiscus*. The identification was confirmed by examining the photographs of the syntypes.

Many similar species are known of which three are especially similar:

Turbonilla pupoides d'Orbigny 1842 (= *phrikalea* Watson 1882): Present in the Caribbean, it is distinguished by numerous spiral striae, two of which are wider, one halfway up the spire and another near the suture. The subsutural depression is more pronounced than in *P. haroldi*.

Turbonilla carlottoi Schander 1994: Species from the African Atlantic coast differs from *P. haroldi* because, in *T. carlottoi* the cords override the axial ribs and the subsutural depression is more pronounced.

Turbonilla ovalis de Folin, 1868: Present in Southeast Asia, Indonesia and the Solomon Islands, it is more pupoid and has a more pronounced labial tooth.

Apart from these three species, others have been described, although with more evident differences but with a similar shape and sculptural pattern, such as the African Atlantic species *Turbonilla kerstinae* Schnader 1994 or the Pacific *Pyrgiscus hebridarum* (Peñas & Rolán 2010).

It has been found in samples collected between 5 and 90 m deep being especially abundant between 10 and 15 meters at Papanui wreck (-12 m) (27 shells), Ruperts Bay (-11 m) (30 shells) and in Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole (-15 m) (40 shells). In the only deep sample (Dawson, at -90 m) only 1 shell has been found.

The only shell studied from Ascension Island (Figs. 10I, J) was a somewhat deteriorated juvenile collected at a depth of 150 meters. It has more ribs and narrower interspaces than *P. haroldi*. Also, the spiral sculpture is somewhat different. Together with its absence in the shallow samples of Ascension, contrary to what happens in Saint Helena, makes us think that we are dealing with a different species that we call *Pyrgiscus* sp. for not being able to compare it with other species.

Strioturbonilla assimilans (E.A. Smith, 1890) n. comb. (Figs. 11, 19J-M)

Original description: *Turbonilla assimilans* E.A. Smith, 1890: 276, pl. 23 fig. 19.

Turbonilla assimilans E.A. Smith, 1890

Turbonilla (*Dunkeria*) *eritima* E.A. Smith, 1890 (in part), new synonym

Type material: 10 syntypes of *Turbonilla assimilans* from the Turton collection (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605708); two syntypes of *T. eritima* (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605710) from the Turton collection, the largest (Fig. 19M herein) here designated as lectotype.

Material examined: 10 syntypes (photograph) and 47 shells from 17 samples of 16 stations: SAINT HELENA • 2 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; in detritus in a cave; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 7 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; in detritus; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; sand, in the cave; 5 Mar. 2014; Brown leg. • 2 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'45.6"S, 5°45'18.0"W; -5 m; in detritus; 7 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 j; Red Rock, Cave near Cat Island; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; in detritus; 9 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 7 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; in sand; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 8 sh; Dawson; 90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 5 sh; Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole; 15°54'40", 5°41'17"W; -15 m; at cave entrance; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Buoy's Hole; -10 m; in sand; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Cat Island; -11 m; near large boulders; 31 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; under large boulders; 7 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Merriman Island; 15°54'43"S, 5°40'10"W; -16 m; in sand; 16 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; in detritus; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 4 j; Bird Island; -12 m; in detritus, in cave-tunnel; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Papanui wreck, close Jamestown; -11 m; base of wreck; 10 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; in detritus, in a cave; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; in detritus; 13 Jan 2015; Peter Wirtz leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena.

Description: Shell elevated, with about six post-nuclear whorls, up to 2.4 × 0.8 mm. Whorls convex, with deep suture; ribs somewhat sigmoid, predominantly orthocone, narrower than their interspaces. Surface of whorls completely covered by equidistant spiral cords which override the ribs (Fig. 11J). In the lower third of the whorls, three wider spiral cords can stand out, of which the middle one is usually less developed (Fig. 11D), the upper one is located approximately one third of the height of the whorl, and the lower one is suprasutural. This latter cord is not surpassed by the axial ribs and marks the base of the shell, which is striated (Fig. 11G). Columella with a very weak fold (Fig. 11F).

Protoconch with a width of 245 µm, of type A tending to B, in which the upper part of the nucleus is visible (Fig. 11E).

Remarks: There is some variability in terms of a more or less convex profile of the whorls, which entails having a more or less deep suture, and also in terms of the number of ribs (from twenty to thirty in the last whorl) (Figs. 11C, D, F, H).

Strioturbonilla assimilans has been found in samples collected between 5 and 90 meters being the Dawson sample (-90m) in which more specimens were counted (8).

SMITH (1890) described and illustrated both *Turbonilla assimilans* (p. 276, pl. 23 fig. 19) and *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima* (p. 276, pl. 23 fig. 22) (Figs. 11A, B). From both descriptions it is deduced that *T. assimilans* is a species of similar appearance to *T. eritima* from which it would differ by reaching a larger size (9-10 whorls and 4.5 mm in height compared to 6 whorls and 3 mm), by having a larger protoconch and fewer ribs on the penultimate whorl (20 versus 22). Ten syntypes of *T. assimilans* and two of *T. eritima* from the Turton collection are deposited in the NHMUK. The study of the photograph of the two syntypes of *T. eritima* seems to indicate that they are

not the same species. One shell, with just over six whorls and 3 mm (Fig. 19M) could correspond to the shell on which Smith relied to make his original description and figure of *T. eritima* while the other shell, a juvenile (Fig. 19N) appears to correspond to a different undescribed species.

The shells we have studied fit better both the description and the syntypes of *T. assimilans* although they seem to show some variability with respect to the convexity of their whorls and with respect to the number of axial ribs that is related to the width of their interspaces (Fig. 19F, H). However, these differences do not seem to indicate different species and the adult syntype (Fig. 19M) of *T. eritima* (presumably the figured specimen in SMITH, 1890a) could fit into this range of variability and is here designated as lectotype of *T. eritima*. Therefore we consider that the taxon *T. eritima* synonymous with *T. assimilans*.

Another issue is to determine its generic placement. *Turbonilla* is an obviously overloaded genus and *Dunkeria* is very different (shell pupoid with reticulate sculpture). Being aware that this is tentative, it has been chosen to give value to the possession of spiral grooves over its entire surface combined with sigmoid ribs and therefore its inclusion in the genus *Strioturbonilla*. It is distinguished from its type species *S. sigmoidea* by having some more marked spiral cords and by its protoconch of type B with partially visible nucleus.

We also want to emphasize that the possession of spiral cords clearly demarcated from the furrows could also be related to some species of the genus *Parthenina* such as *P. emaciata*, a species in which at a great magnification, grooves are also visible, although much weaker, over all the surface.

Another similar species, *Turbonilla arnoldoi* de Jong & Coomans, 1988, a species from Curaçao, has much fewer ribs, more prominent and reaching the base of the shell.

Figure 11. *Strioturbonilla assimilans* (Saint Helena). A: original drawing of *Turbonilla assimilans* (in SMITH, 1890a); B: original drawing of *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima* (in SMITH, 1890a); C: shell (2.4 mm) from Egg Island; D, E: shell (2.1 mm) from Papanui wreck and protoconch; F, G: shell (2.1 mm) from Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole) and microsculpture of its base; H: shell (1.7 mm) from Cat Island; I, J: apical view of a shell from Papanui wreck and of the microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 11. *Strioturbonilla assimilans* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *Turbonilla assimilans* (en SMITH, 1890a); B: dibujo original de *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima* (en E.A. SMITH, 1890a); C: concha (2,4 mm) de Egg Island; D, E: concha (2,1 mm) de Papanui wreck y protoconcha; F, G: concha (2,1 mm) de Bouy's Hole/Cavalley Hole y microescultura de su base; H: concha (1,7 mm) de Cat Island; I, J: vista apical de una concha de Papanui wreck y de la microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Parthenina brachia (E.A. Smith, 1890) n. comb. (Figs. 12, 19F, G)

Original description: *Turbonilla brachia* E.A. Smith, 1890: 276, pl. 23 fig. 21.

Turbonilla brachia E.A. Smith, 1890.

Type material: 9 syntypes from the Turton collection (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605709) and 3 Syntypes in The Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia (cat. 67923).

Material examined: 9 syntypes (photograph) and more than 500 shells, adults and juveniles, in 24 samples: SAINT HELENA • >300 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; 12 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 4 sh; Bennetts Point towards Lady's Chair; -23 m; 15 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Billy May's Revenge; -12 m; 12 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Bird Island; -12 m; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 4 sh; Black Rocks, Flagstaff Bay; -7 m; 7 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 2 sh; Bouy's Hole / Cavalley Hole; 15°54'40", 5°41'17"W; -15 m; 28 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 7 sh; Dawson; -90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 46 sh (26 j); Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; coll. Peter Wirtz leg. • 110 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; 13 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 3 sh (2 j); James Bay; -10 m; 22 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 21 sh; James Bay Mooring; -28 m; 8 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Lighter Rock; 15°57'18"S, 5°45'43.2"W; -26 m; 12 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 5 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Long Ledge; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 15 sh; Long Ledge; -19 m; 2 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; -12 m; 22 May 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 4 sh; Merriman Island; 15°54'43"S, 5°40'10"W; -16 m; 16 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 9 sh; W of Jamestown; 15°55'33.6"S, 5°43'44.4"W; -28 m; near artificial reef; 28 Jun. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 70 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; in sand; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 4 sh; Papanui wreck, near Jamestown; -11 m; 10 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 7 sh; Red Island 15°56'34"S, 5°44'31.2"W; -12 m; 10 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Red Island; -12 m; 30 Dec. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 5 sh; Red Island in Long Ledge; -12 m; 19 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Romans reef; -9 m; 9 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena Island.

Description: Shell small, somewhat cylindrical, with four whorls, up to 1.8 × 0.8 mm in material examined. Profile of whorls flat-convex, somewhat angular at its base (most evident in its last whorl) which makes it have a deep and somewhat ribbed suture. More than twenty axial ribs in each whorl, curved in the form of somewhat sigmoid inverted C (Fig. 12J), wider than their interspaces; upper part of ribs rising slightly above the suture sketching a narrow ribbed ledge (Fig. 12H). The ribs disappear in the basal part of the shell. Occasionally, one or two suprasutural spiral cords above the periphery between the ribs (Fig. 12J, K). Aperture oval, narrowing at top, with a small tooth on the inner lip on a callus that covers a weak umbilical incision (Fig. 12C).

Protoconch type C, 260 μm in diameter (Figs. 12F, H).

Remarks: Although the original drawing is somewhat deficient, Smith's description and the consultation of the

syntypes has allowed us to ensure that it is this species.

There is a lot of variability in terms of the strength of the sculpture between shells with obvious ribs and others with barely emerging ribs, practically smooth and also in terms of the presence or not of spiral cords (Figs. 12E, J).

The dimensions, protoconch and sculpture of the shells place them in *Parthenina*, rather than *Turbonilla*.

More than 500 shells, collected between 5 and 90 meters depth, have been studied. This species has been especially abundant in sand bottoms in Bedgellat Wreck at 18m depth where more than 300 shells were counted.

In Cape Verde Islands, there are two species, *Parthenina faberi* (van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000) and *Chrysalida feldi* (van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000) that are very similar to *P. brachia*. *Parthenina faberi* is more conical and has more pronounced and separated ribs while *P. feldi* has more spiral cords and a less ribbed suture.

Parthenina stanyi n. sp (Fig. 13)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:DDE40ABC-160A-4ACD-8429-BC06055F6BF5

Type material and type locality: *Holotype*. ASCENSION • 1 sh.; Georgetown; 07°54'38.0"S, 14°26'39.2"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 3, Andy Richardson leg.; RBINS, Brussels n° I.G. 34553 (MT. 2950). *Paratypes*. ASCENSION • 1 sh; same data as the holotype; private collection of F. Swinnen • 2 sh; Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg.; MNCN n° 15.05/200207 • 2 sh; Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg.; MNHN-IM-2022-11299.

Material examined: the type material and 4 additional shells (lost during microscopic preparation) in 2 samples: ASCENSION: • 2 sh (lost); Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg. • 2 sh. (lost); Georgetown; 07°54'38.0"S, 14°26'39.2"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 3, Andy Richardson leg.

Etymology: The species name is dedicated to Stany Vanderhoydonck for his longtime friendship with the second author.

Description: Shell cylindrical, very fragile, minute, with three whorls, up to 1.0 × 0.5 mm. Spire profile somewhat convex, more pronounced in its basal part which accentuates the depth of the suture. Ribs curved and not very prominent, barely noticeable at the base of the shell, wider than their interspaces and whose upper part forms a weak subsutural shelf (Fig. 13E). Entire surface of shell covered by very faint spiral grooves, difficult to see even at a great magnification (Fig. 13B); spiral grooves deeper in some shells in the basal part of their whorls, resulting in visible weak spiral cords between the ribs (Figs. 13C, D). Aperture oval. Columella with a weak curvature, and below an expansion of the inner lip that expands over a weak umbilical fissure.

Protoconch type C, 260 µm wide (Fig. 13E).

Remarks: Despite being very similar to *Parthenina brachia*, this species differs by its smaller size and a less obvious tooth. The most significant point is that it has only been found at depths greater than 100 m while *P. brachia* is abundantly found in shallow waters. Few shells could be studied, maybe because of the small size, but we believe that its absence in shallow water of Ascension contrasts with the abundance of *P. brachia* in shallow waters of Saint Helena. We have considered that these small morphological differences, together with the different bathymetry of its habitat and its insularity justify its description as a species different from *P. brachia* and new to science.

Chrysallida feldi (van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 2000) from Cape Verde is also very similar although it is somewhat larger and has definite spiral cords.

Sayella glaphyra (E.A. Smith, 1890) n. comb. (Figs. 14, 15, 19O, P)

Original Description: *Odostomia glaphyra* E.A. Smith, 1890: 275, pl. 23 fig. 18.
Odostomia glaphyra, E.A. Smith, 1890.

(Right page) Figure 12. *Parthenina brachia* (Saint Helena). A: original drawing of *Turbonilla brachia* (in SMITH, 1890a); B-D: shell, (1.6 mm) from Papanui wreck, detail of the labial tooth and teleoconch sculpture; E: shell (1.5 mm) from Papanui wreck; F: apical view of the protoconch of a shell from Bedgellet wreck; G, H: different views of the protoconch, shells from Papanui wreck; I: shell (1.4 mm) from Papanui wreck; J, K: shell (1.3 mm) from Bedgellet wreck and detail of the spiral cord of the teleoconch; L: lateral view of a shell (1.8 mm) from Bedgellet wreck; M: shell (1.8 mm) from Bedgellet Wreck.

Figura 12. *Parthenina brachia* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *Turbonilla brachia* (en SMITH, 1890a); B-D: concha, (1,6mm) de Papanui wreck, detalle del diente labial y de la escultura de la teleoconcha; E: concha (1,5 mm) de Papanui wreck; F: vista apical de protoconcha de una concha de Bedgellat wreck; G, H: distintas vistas de la protoconcha de Papanui wreck; I: concha (1,4 mm) de Papanui wreck; J, K: concha (1,3 mm) de Bedgellat wreck y detalle del cordón espiral de la teleoconcha; L: vista lateral de una concha (1,8 mm) de Bedgellat wreck; M: concha (1,8 mm) de Bedgellat Wreck.

Figure 13. *Parthenina stanyi* n. sp (Ascension Island). A: shell (1.1 mm) from Georgetown station 2; 7°53.505'S, 14°25.990'W, -130 m; B: shell (0.9 mm) from Georgetown station 2; 7°53.505'S, 14°25.990'W, -130 m; C, D: holotype (1.0 mm) from Georgetown station 3, 7°54.633'S, 14°26.654'W, and detail of its microsculpture; E: apex of another shell from Georgetown station 3, 7°54.633'S, 14°26.654'W.

Figura 13: *Parthenina stanyi* (Isla Ascensión). A: concha (1,1 mm) de Georgetown estación 2 7°53.505'S, 14°25.990'W: -130 m; B: concha (0,9 mm) de Georgetown estación 2 7°53.505'S, 14°25.990'W: -130 m; C, D: holotipo (1,0 mm) de Georgetown estación 3, 7°54.633'S, 14°26.654'W y detalle de su microescultura; E: ápice de otra concha de Georgetown estación 3, 7°54.633'S, 14°26.654'W.

Type material: 4 syntypes from the Turton collection (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605707).

Material examined: 4 syntypes (photograph) and 238 shells, adults and juveniles, in 23 samples: SAINT HELENA • 4 sh; Bend Island; -17 m; 16 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 11 sh; Billy May's Revenge; -12 m; 12 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 14 sh; Bird Island, -12 m; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 6 sh; Bird Shit towards Banks; 15°54'43.2"S, 5°43'32.4"W; 22 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 16 sh; Black Rocks; -7 m; 7 Oct. 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 8 sh; Buoy's Hole; -10 m; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Buttermilk Point; -11 m; 04 Jul. 2015; Leeann Henry leg. • 15 sh; Cat Island; -11 m; 31 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry, leg. • 19 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 19 sh; Frontier Wreck; -28 m; 13 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 3 sh; Lot's Wife Ponds; 16°00'50.6"S, 5°43'33.60"W; -1 m; 20 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 6 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 5 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 6 sh; Long Ledge East; -12 m; 22 May 2015; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh, Merriman Point; -10 m; 8 Aug. 2015; Leeann Henry & Judith Brown, leg. • 3 sh, Merriman Island; 15°54'43"S, 5°40'10"W; -16 m; 16 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry, leg. • 23 sh; Papanui wreck; -12 m; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry, leg. • 3 sh; Peaked; -20 m; 09 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 32 sh; Red Island; -12 m; 30 Dec. 2015; Leeann Henry, leg. • 2 sh+2 frg; Red Rock Cave near Cat Island; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; 9 Mar 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 15 sh; Romans reef; -9 m; 9 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 10 sh; Ruperts Bay; -11 m; 25 Apr. 2017; Leeann Henry, leg. • 2 sh; Ruperts

(Right page) Figure 14. *Sayella glaphyra* (Saint Helena). A: original drawing of *O. glaphyra* (in SMITH, 1890a); B, C: shells (1.9 mm and 2.6 mm) from Papanui wreck, -12 m; D-F: shell (2.4 mm) from Youngs Valley, 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.60"W, -7 m, columellar tooth and protoconch; G, H: detail of the lip insertion and microsculpture of the teleoconch, same locality; I: protoconch of a shell from Papanui wreck, -12 m; J: protoconch from from Youngs Valley, -7 m.

Figura 14. *Sayella glaphyra* (Santa Elena). A: dibujo original de *O. glaphyra* (en SMITH, 1890a); B, C: conchas (1,9 mm y 2,6 mm) de Papanui wreck, -12 m; D-F: concha (2,4 mm) de Youngs Valley, 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.60"W, -7 m, diente columelar y protoconcha; G, H: detalle de la inserción labial y de la microestructura de la teleoconcha, misma localidad; I: protoconcha (Papanui wreck, -12 m); J: protoconcha de Youngs Valley, -7 m.

Jetty; -11 m; 5 Oct. 2015; Leeann Henry, leg. • 17 sh; Youngs Valley; 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.60"W; -7 m; 01 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg.

Material examined (*Sayella* cf. *glaphyra*, Fig. 15): 73 shells, adults and juveniles, in 23 samples. ASCENSION: • 1 sh; Boatswain Bird Island; -10 m; 16 Apr. 2017; Sarah Browning-Lee leg. • 1 sh; Boatswain Bird Island; -27 m; 26 Nov. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee y Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Boatswain Bird Island; -33 m; 12 Feb. 2017; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Boatswain Bird Island; -35 m; 16 Apr. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 4 sh; Catherine Point, Arches, Georgetown; -23 m; 27 Mar. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Clarence Bay Arch; -24 m; 16 Oct. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 14 sh; English Bay, 7°53'25.42"S, 14°22'50.24"W; -9 m; 11 Nov. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 14 sh; English Bay; -9 m; 8 Feb. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh; Georgetown; 07°53'30.3"S, 14°25'59.4"W; -130 m; 21 Feb. 2018; Fishing vessel "Extractor" station 2, Andy Richardson leg. • 1 sh; Horse Shoe Reef; -14 m; 6 Mar. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Horse Shoe Reef; -23 m; 23 Oct. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Ladies Loo; -21 m; 21 Feb. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; North Ascension Island; 07°52'35.1"S, 14°23'32"W; -150 m; 25 Feb. 2019; Andy Richardson leg. • 2 sh; North East Point; -24 m; 4 Dec. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; North Point; -23 m; 11 Mar. 2017; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; One Hook; -20 m; 5 Jun. 2016; Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; One Hook, English Bay; -18.4 m; 4 Oct. 2015; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Red Rock; -15 m; 17 Dec. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Rocky reef between Beach and Derby Wreck; beached; 27 Sep. 2015; Sarah Browning-Lee and Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; "Triangles", 7°53'21.39"N, 14°22'44.72"W; -15 m; 19 Jul. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh; White island; -18 m; 6 Feb. 2017; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Wiggan Pier; -11 m; 31 Dec. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg. • 5 sh; Wiggan Pier; -13 m; 1 Feb. 2016; Sarah Browning-Lee & Judith Brown leg.

Type locality: Saint Helena Island.

Description: Shell with six whorls, up to 2.6 × 1 mm, cylindrical, somewhat pupoid. Whorls planoconvex with a shallow and slightly stepped suture. No axial sculpture except for the somewhat prosocline growth lines; spiral sculpture formed by weak striations visible at high magnification predominantly at the base of the shell (Figs. 14G, H). Aperture oval, narrow at its top. Columella with a small, internal fold often not visible in the frontal position (Fig. 14E).

Protoconch type C, 300 µm wide.

Remarks: Smith defined and figured *Odostomia glaphyra* (p. 278, pl. 23 fig. 23). Both description and measurements coincide with the specimens studied. Although Smith originally included this species in the genus *Odostomia*, we do not believe that this can be maintained. The genus *Odostomia* J. Fleming, 1813 has been used as a kind of catch-all where they included most of the pyramidellids that were not very tall and lacked sculpture. This caused the number of *Odostomia* species to be excessive. In recent years, historical

genera and subgenera such as *Megastomia*, *Brachystomia*, *Liostomia*, *Eulimastoma*, among others, are being recovered, which, recovering the generic value, try to alleviate the numerical burden of *Odostomia* s.l. which will undoubtedly favour subsequent taxonomic revisions or anatomical and/or genetic studies.

The type species of *Odostomia*, *Odostomia plicata* (Montagu, 1803) has a clearly conical shell with an evident columellar tooth, something that clearly differentiates it from our species, which is why we have thought it appropriate to assign it to a different genus.

Several genera of Pyramidellids are characterized, like ours, by having a moderate height (taller than *Odostomia* but less than *Eulimella* or *Syrnola*), absence of significant sculpture and lack of a clear columellar tooth:

Doliella Monterosato 1880 has *Doliella nitens* as its only species (Jeffreys, 1870). It is a deep-sea species that lacks a columellar fold.

Sayella Dall, 1885 is a genus whose type species, *Sayella hemphilli* (Dall,

Figure 15. *Sayella* cf. *glaphyra* from English Bay (Ascension Island), 7°53'25.42"S, 14°22'50.24"W, -9 m. A: shell (2.0 mm); B: shell (2.35 mm); C: apical view of the protoconch; D-G: shell (2.0 mm), detail of its aperture and columellar fold, detail of the microsculpture of the base of the shell and detail of the subsutural microsculpture; H: protoconch.

Figura 15. Sayella cf. *glaphyra* de English Bay (Isla Ascensión), 7°53'25,42"S, 14°22'50,24"W, -9 m: A: concha (2,0 mm); B: concha (2,35 mm); C: vista apical de la protoconcha; D-G: concha (2,0 mm), detalle de su abertura y pliegue columelar, detalle de la microescultura de la base de la concha y detalle de la microescultura subsutural; H: protoconcha.

1884), among other characteristics, is characterized by having an elevated shell, somewhat pupoid, with a columellar fold. Although in the original description, spiral microsculpture is not mentioned, MORRISON (1939) indicates

that microsculpture is usual in the genus.

Petitilla J. B. Wise 1997 is a genus (proposed by J. B. Wise in 1996 as *Petitella*) whose type species *Petitilla crosseana* (= *Sayella*, Dall, 1885) has a

shell very similar to that of *Sayella hemphilli* but has anatomical differences that justify its change of genus. Given the impossibility of being able to differentiate on the basis of shell characters alone, between the genera *Sayella* and *Petitilla* and since our specimens lack animals, we are chosen to use the senior genus *Sayella*.

On the other hand, there seems to be some diversity regarding the size of the shell. Some were larger, with five whorls and 2.4 mm in height, and others were smaller (five whorls, 1.9 mm), with no other significant morphological differences between them. The small number of specimens studied has not allowed us to verify the existence of specimens of interme-

diante size, so we do not rule out the possibility of encountering two cryptic species.

The specimens studied from Ascension Island (Fig. 15) are more ovoid and their whorls are more convex, so the aperture is more rounded. There are no significant differences in the fold of the columella, the spiral microsculpture or in its protoconch. In addition, it also seems to have the same size variability seen in those of Saint Helena. That is why we have preferred to refer to it as *Sayella* cf. *glaphyra*.

In both St. Helena and Ascension the species appears to be abundant and widely distributed given the high number of shells and seasons in which it has been located.

Odostomia lukisii Jeffreys, 1859 (Fig. 16)

Original description: Jeffreys, 1859: 112-113; pl. 3 fig. 19 a-b

Type material: Syntypes from Guernsey (Channel Isles), USNM 132156.

Material examined: 47 shells in 13 samples: SAINT HELENA • 2 sh; Approaching Young's Valley; 15°55'44.4"S, 5°43'51.6"W; -7 m; 1 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 2 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; 12 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Bird Shit towards Banks; 15°54'43.2"S, 5°43'32.4"W; 22 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 3 sh; Buoy's Hole; -10 m; 21 May 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 15 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 3 sh; Lighter Rock; 15°57'18"S, 5°45'43.2"W; -26 m; 12 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 5 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 5 sh; Long Ledge; -19 m; 2 Apr. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; W of Jamestown; 15°55'33.6"S, 5°43'44.4"W; -28 m; near artificial reef; 28 Jun. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 7 sh; Papanui wreck; -1 m; 17 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh; Red Island; 15°56'34"S, 5°44'31.2"W; -12 m; 10 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown, leg. • 3 sh; Red Rock, Cave near Cat Island; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -19 m; 9 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown, leg.

Description: Oval conical shell that with four whorls reaches 1.9 mm in height and 1.0 mm in width. Whorls flattened convex with shallow slightly stepped suture. It lacks sculpture except for orthocline growth lines and a very faint subsutural depression. Aperture almond-shaped, nearly oval, with a poorly developed columellar tooth on a very weak umbilical fissure.

Protoconch type C, about 290 µm in diameter.

Remarks: *O. lukisii* is a known species with a wide distribution that has been addressed in numerous studies:

RODRIGUEZ BABÍO & THIRIOT-QUIÉVREUX (1975), AARTSEN, MENKHORST & GITTEBERGER (1984), FRETTER, GRAHAM & ANDREWS (1986), PEÑAS, TEMPLADO & MARTINEZ (1996), PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999), ÖZTÜRK, BAKIR & MICALI (2013), HØISÆTER (2014), GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014). It is distributed from the Baltic Sea, the European Atlantic coast from Norway, the entire Mediterranean, and the African coast to Angola, and also in some Macaronesian islands such as the Azores, Canary Islands and Madeira. This study extends its distribution to the island of Saint Helena.

Figure 16. *Odostomia lukisii* (Saint Helena). A: shell (1.9 mm) from Papanui wreck, -12 m; B: shell (1.7 mm), same locality; C: protoconch, same locality; D-F: shell (1.2 mm) from Long Ledge, -19 m, detail of the subsutural depression and view of the columellar tooth and the umbilical fissure; G, H: shell (1.4 mm) from Long Ledge, -19 m and detail of the suture and growth lines.

Figura 16. Odostomia lukisii (Santa Elena). A: concha (1,9 mm) de Papanui wreck, -12 m; B: concha (1,7 mm), misma localidad; C: protoconcha, misma localidad; D-F: concha (1,2 mm) de Long Ledge, -19 m, detalle de la depresión subsutural y vista del diente columelar y de la fisura umbilical; G, H: concha (1,4 mm) de Long Ledge, -19 m y detalle de la sutura y de las líneas de crecimiento.

Odostomia lucsegersi n. sp. (Fig. 17)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:AA12AC0A-48C7-4CD1-A1E4-9FFC1D1886A4

Type material and type locality: *Holotype*. SAINT HELENA • 1 sh; Horse Pasture Point; -16 m; 25 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. 160625/148; RBINS, Brussels n° I.G.34553 (MT.3951). *Paratypes*. SAINT HELENA • 4 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg.; MNCN n° 15.05/200206P • 4 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg.; MNHN-IM-2022-11295 • 2 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 21 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg.; private collection of F. Swinnen.

Material examined: The type material and 15 more shells, in 10 samples: SAINT HELENA • 1 sh; Bedgellat Wreck; 15°56'53"S, 5°45'30"W; -18 m; 12 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Bird Island; -12 m; 16 Jan. 2015; Peter Wirtz leg. • 2 sh; Black Rocks NR Thompsons Valley; -20 m; 15 May 2017; Leeann Henry leg. • 4 sh; Dawson; -90 m; 8 Apr. 2018; Leeann Henry leg. • 3 sh; Egg Island; -29 m; 27 Jan. 2014; Peter Wirtz leg. • 1 sh; Horse Pasture Point; -16 m; 25 Jun. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Long Ledge; 15°56'42"S, 5°45'10.8"W; -11 m; 5 Mar. 2014; Judith Brown leg. • 1 sh; Merriman Island; 15°54'43"S, 5°40'10"W; -16 m; 16 Jul. 2016; Leeann Henry leg. • 1 sh; Red Island in Long Ledge; -12 m; 19 Jul. 2014; Judith Brown leg.

Etymology: Named after Luc Segers a longtime friend of the second autor.

Description: Shell conical that with five teleoconch whorls reaches 1.9×0.8 mm. Flat spiral profile with a slight convex tendency in some specimens. Shallow suture but highlighted at the bottom of the whorls by a more pronounced suprasutural narrowing as the shell grows (Fig. 17E). Except for the prosocline growth lines, no other sculpture can be seen.

Aperture rhomboid. Outer lip with somewhat angular periphery. Small but obvious columellar tooth (Fig. 17F). It presents a weak umbilical fissure (Fig. 17F).

Protoconch of type B with about 200 μm in diameter (Figs. 17C, G, K).

Remarks: PIMENTA & ABSALÃO (2004b) in their revision of the genus *Eulimastoma* Bartsch, 1916 (type species *Eulimastoma dotella* (Dall & Bartsch, 1909)) from Brazil commented that, although this genus is well characterized (ODÉ & SPEERS, 1972), it has not been contemplated in recent revisions of the European Pyramidellidae although some species could be better placed in the genus *Eulimastoma* than in *Odostomia*. It is evident that the genus *Odostomia* has been used as a catch-all and that it is overburdened with species. We believe it is convenient to subdivide it (as is already being done by raising the rank of some subgenres or recovering historical genera) and we share with Pimenta & Absalão the need to unify classification criteria on both sides of the Atlantic. Our species, *O. lucsegersi*, is halfway between *Eulimastoma*, and *Odostomia* (it presents the suture in the form of a V but lacks a suprasutural cord, both

characters present in *E. dotella*). We have preferred as long as there is no revision of the genus *Odostomia* to keep ours in this genus because of its resemblance to the African species *O. paardekooperi*.

Odostomia paardekooperi van Aartsen, Gittenberger & Goud, 1998 is the most similar to ours. Although its authors indicate that it has a protoconch of type C, the photograph of the holotype clearly shows that it is of type B as later indicated by PEÑAS AND ROLÁN (1999). Our species differs from this by being smaller in size (it does not reach 2 mm compared to 2.8 mm of the holotype of *O. paardekooperi*), by having a deeper suture and by having a protoconch of type B tending to type A in which in some shells a minimum fraction of its nucleus is seen.

O. turrita Hanley, 1844 is distinguished by having protoconch clearly of type A and superficial spiral striations. *O. unidentata* (Montagu, 1803) also has a clear type A protoconch with the nucleus well visible and the first whorl with spiral sculpture. *Eulimastoma canaliculatum* (C.B. Adams, 1858), a species widely distributed along the western Atlantic coast, is distinguished by being larger (holotype with 6 whorls and 3.2 mm in height) and by having a protoconch of type C.

Odostomia lucsegersi has been found in samples up to 90 m. The largest number of shells (10, more than 1/3 of those studied) were counted among the debris collected from a cave 11 meters deep in Long Ledge.

(Right page) Figure 17. *Odostomia lucsegersi* n. sp. (Saint Helen). A-C: holotype (1.9 mm) from Horse Pasture Point, -16 m and protoconch; D-F: shell (1.5 mm) from Merriman Island, -16 m, detail of the columellar tooth and the insertion of the external lip; G, H: shell (1.4 mm) from Long Ledge, -11 m and protoconch; I: shell (paratype, 1 mm), same locality; J, K: shell (paratype) and protoconch, same locality.

Figura 17. *Odostomia lucsegersi* n. sp. (Santa Elena). A-C: holotipo (1,9 mm) de Horse Pasture Point, -16 m y protoconcha; D-F: concha (1,5 mm) de Merriman Island, -16 m, detalle del diente columelar y de la inserción del labio externo; G, H: concha (paratipo, 1,4 mm) de Long Ledge, -11 m y protoconcha; I: concha (paratipo, 1 mm), misma localidad; J, K: concha (paratipo) y protoconcha, misma localidad.

Figure 18. *Odostomia templadoi* n. sp. from Grattan Seamount (Ascension). A-C: holotype (1.2 mm), detail of the lip insertion and columellar tooth; D: protoconch; E, F: shell (paratype, 1.1 mm) and detail of its microsculpture; G, H: shells (paratypes, 1.1 mm).

Figura 18. Odostomia templadoi n. sp. de Grattan Seamount (Ascension). A-C: holotipo (1,2 mm), detalle de la inserción labial y diente columelar; D: protoconcha; E, F: concha (paratipo, 1,1 mm) y detalle de su microescultura; G, H: conchas (paratipos, 1,1 mm).

Odostomia templadoi n. sp. (Fig. 18)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:477D8654-D07B-4C12-A1B4-14EDBBEF7B92

Type material and type locality: *Holotype*. ASCENSION • 1 sh; Grattan Seamount; 9°4,314'S, 12°48,695'W; -90 to -100 m; 25 Jan. 2015; Andy Richardson, leg.; RBINS, Brussels n° I.G. 34552. *Paratypes*. ASCENSION • 3 shells; same data as the holotype; MNCN n° 15.05/200205 • 3 shells; same data as the holotype; MNHN-IM-2922-11296 • 2 shells; same data as the holotype; private collection of F. Swinnen collection.

Material examined: The type material and 6 additional shells in one sample: ASCENSION: • 6 sh; Grattan Seamount; 09°04'18.8"S, 12°48'41,7"W; -90 m to -100 m; 25 Jan. 2015; Andy Richardson leg.

Etymology: The specific name is after José Templado, biologist and important scientist working in the MNCN.

Description: Shell small, conical-oval that with a little more than three whorls reaches a size of 1.2×0.6 mm. Whorls flat-convex, somewhat depressed at its base, which accentuates the depth of its suture. No sculpture except for prosocline growth lines and very faint spiral striae, visible at high magnification in the subsutural area (Fig. 18F). Aperture oval. Columella with prominent but somewhat internal tooth (Fig. 18C). It has a narrow umbilical fissure.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this study, samples have been taken at 42 points on Saint Helena at a depth between -1 and -29 meters (one deeper at -90m). On Ascension Island, samples were taken at 41 points, from the coastline to -150 meters, most between -6 and -35 meters. 6 samples were taken deeper than -60 m.

On Saint Helena island, in 62% of the points sampled yielded between 3 and 5 different species. In three samples a single species was found and 7, 8 and 9 species were found respectively in three other samples. The sampling points in which more species were found were: Bird Island (-12 m) with 7, Papanui wreck (-12 m) with 8 and Egg Island (-29 m) with 9 species.

On Ascension Island, most of the samples (71%) contained only one species of pyramidellid. Only in one sample, Georgetown station 2 ($07^{\circ}53'30.3''S$, $14^{\circ}25'59.4''W$, -130 m) 5 species were found.

On the island of Saint Helena, Smith cited twelve species of Pyramidellidae. Eight of them have been found again, identified, photographed and redescribed: *Pyramidella dolabrata*, *Obeliscus (Syrnola) sanctahelenae*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides*, *T. haroldi*, *T. brachia*, *T. (Dunkeria) assimilans*, *Leucotina minuta*, y *Odostomia glaphyra*. *Turbonilla (D.) eritima* is here treated as a synonym of *T. (D.) assimilans*.

Cingulina circinata, described by Smith for Saint Helena, has been consid-

ered not to correspond to the original species but is here considered as an undescribed new species, *Cingulina boirai* n. sp.

Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio has not been found in the present study. *Cingulina (Mathilda) quadricarinata* is not considered today to belong to the family Pyramidellidae. In addition, two more species of Pyramidellids have been located, *Miralda verhaeghei* n. sp. and *Odostomia lucsegersi* n. sp. which are considered new to science. Finally, *Odostomia lukisii*, a well-known species with a wide distribution, has been located bringing the total number of Pyramidellidae of Saint Helena to 13.

For seven species, it has been thought appropriate to replace Smith's original generic assignments. Thus *Obeliscus (Syrnola) sanctahelenae* would be recombined as *Tiberia sactahelenae*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides* as *Odostomella truncatelloides*, *T. haroldii* as *Pyrgiscus haroldii*, *T. (Dunkeria) assimilans* as *Strioturbonilla assimilans*, *T. brachia* as *Parthenina brachia*, *Leucotina minuta* as *Menestho minuta*, and *Odostomia glaphyra* as *Sayella glaphyra*.

Photographs of the syntypes of *Obeliscus (Syrnola) sactahelenae*, *Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio*, *Turbonilla truncatelloides*, *Turbonilla haroldi*, *Turbonilla brachia*, *Leucotina minuta*, *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) assimilans* and *Odostomia glaphyra* are presented on Figure 19.

Table I. Distribution of the species between Saint Helena and Ascension islands.

Tabla I. Distribución de las especies entre las islas de Santa Elena y Ascensión.

SAINT HELENA	ASCENSIÓN
<i>Pyramidella dolabrata</i>	<i>Pyramidella dolabrata</i>
<i>Tiberia sanctaehelenae</i>	<i>Tiberia</i> cf. <i>sanctaehelenae</i>
<i>Odostomella truncatelloides</i>	<i>Odostomella</i> cf. <i>truncatelloides</i>
	<i>Odostomella</i> cf. <i>fonteini</i>
<i>Cingulina boirai</i> n. sp.	
<i>Miralda verhaeghei</i> n. sp.	
<i>Menestho minuta</i>	
<i>Pyrgiscus haroldi</i>	<i>Pyrgiscus</i> sp.
<i>Strioturbonilla assimilans</i>	
<i>Parthenina brachia</i>	
	<i>Parthenina stanyi</i> n.sp
<i>Sayella glaphyra</i>	<i>Sayella</i> cf. <i>glaphyra</i>
<i>Odostomia lucsegersi</i> n. sp.	
<i>Odostomia lukisii</i>	
	<i>Odostomia templadoi</i> n. sp.
<i>Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio</i>	
13 species (3 new)	8 species (2 new)

As for Ascension Island, 8 species of Pyramidellids have been studied. As the only pyramidellid cited in ROSEWATER (1975) is *Pyramidella dolabrata* the remaining seven are new contributions to the island's fauna.

Four of them are similar to others already described so are presented as "confer". Of these, *Sayella* cf. *glaphyra*, *Tiberia* cf. *sactaehelenae* and *Odostomella* cf. *truncatelloides* bear resemblance to others from Saint Helena while *Odostomella* cf. *fonteini* is similar to a species from the American coast. One species has been assigned only generically (*Pyrgiscus* sp.) and two others are new to

science: *Odostomia templadoi* n. sp. and *Parthenina stanyi* n. sp.

In total, 18 species have been counted between the two islands (Table I). Two of them *P. dolabrata* and *O. lukisii* are also found in other localities. *P. dolabrata* is found on both islands and has a wide distribution located in the Indian Ocean and on both sides of the Atlantic. *O. lukisii* is located on the island of Saint Helena and also on the eastern Atlantic coasts and the Mediterranean. Furthermore, *O. cf. fonteini* is a species found on the island of Ascension, not found on Saint Helena but recorded in the Caribbean and on the coasts of Brazil.

Fig. 19. Type specimens of SMITH (1890a). A. *Obeliscus (Syrnola) sanctaehelenae* Smith, 1890, syntype (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605706); B: *Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio* Smith, 1890, syntype (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605705); C-D: *Turbonilla truncatelloides* Smith, 1890, syntypes (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605712); E: *Turbonilla baroldi* Smith, 1890, syntype, (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605711); F, G: *Turbonilla brachia* Smith, 1890, syntypes (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605709); H, I: *Leucotina minuta* Smith, 1890, syntypes (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605713); J-L: *Turbonilla assimilans* Smith, 1890, syntypes (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605708); M-N: *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima* Smith, 1890, M: lectotype, N: paralectotype (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605710); O, P: *Odostomia glaphyra* Smith, 1890, syntypes (NHMUK: ecatalogue 5605707).

Fig. 19. *Especímenes tipo de SMITH (1890a)*. A: *Obeliscus (Syrnola) sanctaehelenae* Smith, 1890, *sintipo* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605706); B: *Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilio* Smith, 1890, *sintipo* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605705); C, D: *Turbonilla truncatelloides* Smith, 1890, *sintipos* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605712); E: *Turbonilla haroldi* Smith, 1890, *sintipo* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605711); F, G: *Turbonilla brachia* Smith, 1890, *sintipos* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605709); H, I: *Leucotina minuta* Smith, 1890, *sintipos* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605713); J-L: *Turbonilla assimilans* Smith, 1890, *sintipos* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605708); M, N: *Turbonilla (Dunkeria) eritima* Smith, 1890, M: *lectotipo*, N: *paralectotipo* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605710); O, P: *Odostomia glaphyra* Smith, 1890, *sintipos* (NHMUK: *ecatalogue* 5605707).

O. truncatelloides, *S. glaphyra* and *sac-tae-helenae* are found on both islands if confirmed to be conspecific.

Cingulina boirai n. sp., *Miralda ver-haeghei* n. sp., *Menestho minuta*, *Pyrgiscus haroldii*, *Pyrgiscus assimilans*, *Parthenina brachia*, *Odostomia lucsegersi* would be endemic to Saint Helena. *Obeliscus (Syrnola) pumilo* could also be although they have not been found in this study. *Parthenina stanyi* and *Odostomia templadoi* n. sp., would be endemic to Ascension.

The number of species of pyramidellids present on both islands is scarce, taking into account the high number of samples studied and the number of specimens studied (which in some species exceeds four hundred specimens), if we compare it with the 73 species of pyramidellids present in the Canary Islands (HERNANDEZ ET AL., 2011) or the 66 species cited in Cape Verde (ROLÁN, 2005). These figures are not surprising and are related to the difficulty for parasitic organisms to colonize new habitats, the lower variety of habitats associated with the small extension of these islands and the remoteness to the continents or other neighbouring islands.

The colonizing species of Saint Helena and Ascension could have come from both coasts. In the case of Saint Helena, species such as *Odostomia lukisii* and *Cingulina boirai* n. sp. seem to indicate a preferably African origin. On the other hand, on the island of Ascension *Odostomella* cf. *fonteini* seems to indicate a preferably American origin. *Sayella glaphyra*, which also seems to have an American origin, also points out that between both islands there has also been a transfer of species. The rest of the species are more difficult to interpret.

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